

Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis Distributions, Stability and Information Decoding

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Given an ideal gas with N particles and a total energy E_{total} , one may argue that there is a possibility for it to achieve equilibrium. Loosely speaking, this should mean that $p(e_i)$ values ($e_i =$ single particle values) remain constant in time. The problem is that there are many $p(e_i)$ sets which satisfy $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ ((1a)) and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{total}/N$ ((1b)). Only one should physically appear for equilibrium. Otherwise these sets, which may be infinitesimally different, could lead to the system continuously changing its $p(e_i)$ values, but be in equilibrium which is a contradiction as it is changing macroscopically in time.

The question is: How does one obtain the correct $p(e_i)$ set? The original Maxwell-Boltzmann type approach is to maximize \ln (for math simplicity) the number of arrangements: $\ln(N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!)$ subject to the two constraints ((1)) Stirling's approximation is used to obtain the average of the \ln function through $\ln(n(e_i)!)$ approx = $n \ln(n(e_i))$. Alternatively, one may take Shannon's entropy a priori and maximize it subject to the constraints. In this way, one does not have to worry about maximizing the number of states or Stirling's approximation. \ln is directly introduced by Shannon so that $\ln(p(e_1)p(e_2)) = \ln(p(e_1)) + \ln(p(e_2))$ and Shannon's entropy is the negative of the average information - $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$. Still a third approach is to use reaction balance.

We wish to consider a different approach subject to the constraints ((1)) and the idea that there is a unique $p(e_i)$ set. A unique solution may be found if one suggests that there is an information decoder function $F(p(e_i))$ which is able to retrieve e_i information from the equilibrium $p(e_i)$. In other words, this is a statistical problem and $p(e_i)$ is the special statistical solution. All other information in the system should follow mathematically from $p(e_i)$. This suggests the idea of a decoder function, but there must also be stability.

If there is a fluctuation in $p(e_i)$, i.e. $p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$, then the change in the average of the information is 0, i.e. there is stability. If $F(p(e_i))$ decodes the moment of e_i information, i.e. $F(p(e_i)) = ae_i + b$ for ((1)), then $p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) = 1$ ((2)) is the condition for no change in the average decoding versus a $dp(e_i)$ change in the constraints. The idea of the information decoder function is that if there is a unique set of $p(e_i)$ which define the equilibrium, then they essentially (on average) define all information in the system and all information should be written in terms of this special $p(e_i)$ equilibrium set. A slight fluctuation $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ should not destabilize the system. Thus, it is as if nature is reading information in the equilibrium idea gas through the decoder function $F(p(e_i))$. There is no idea of adding information or of maximizing states in this approach.

Mathematically, a change in $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ as the argument of a function involves $dF/dp(e_i)$ from a Taylor expansion. One requires $p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) = dp(e_i)$ ((3)) in order that this sum to 0 (together with $F(p(e_i)) = ae_i + b$). Hence there is a unique decoder function $F(p(e_i))$ and hence $p(e_i)$. $p(e_i)$ is the inverse of F . Alternatively, one might argue that given that $dp(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = ae_i + b$, one could also have $p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) = ae_i + b$. $p dF/dp = 1$ leads to $F = \ln(p)$, while the second condition leads to $F = p(e_i)$ power q . We note that there is a close relationship between $\ln(x)$ and x power n in terms of derivatives. In fact, $d/dx x$ power $n = n x$ power $n-1$ which includes all powers except x power -1 . This is only delivered by $d/dx \ln(x)$. As a result, we

suggest that this approach gives rise to both the Maxwell-Boltzmann $\ln(p)$ as well as the Tsallis distribution. The other traditional approaches do not yield the Tsallis distribution together with the MB one.

Traditional Approaches

Traditional approaches to finding the equilibrium $p(e_i)$ include maximization of the \ln of the number of states subject to the constraints:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = \langle e \rangle \quad ((1b)),$$

maximization of Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ subject to ((1)) or reaction balance.

In the case of the \ln of the number of states one uses:

$$\ln(N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!) \quad \text{with Stirling's approximation:} \quad \ln(n(e_i)!) \approx n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) \quad ((4))$$

In Shannon's entropy case, the \ln does not arise from Stirling's approximation, but is chosen a priori so that information $\ln(p(e_i))$ is additive. We suggest that this approach is suggestive of an information decoder. In particular, one takes $p(e_i)$ and applies a decoder function \ln to it to extract information. We suggest, however, that this decoder function can be more general than $\ln(p(e_i))$. We suggest that one should be able to obtain both the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and the Tsallis one at the same time instead of only obtaining the Maxwell-Boltzmann one through these traditional approaches.

Information Decoder

An equilibrium (ideal gas) consists of a unique $p(e_i)$ set which satisfies ((1a)) ((1b)) even though mathematically many such sets exist. If these sets differ infinitesimally, then an observer might see $p(e_i)$ values change in time which would not be an equilibrium situation. Thus, one must find a stable unique $p(e_i)$ set.

We have suggested in previous notes that a statistical system such as an ideal gas is described in terms of averages of e_i moments, i.e. e_i power 0 ((1a)) and e_i power 1 ((1b)). The problem, as noted, is that many $p(e_i)$ sets produce the same moment values for these two moments.

Taking Shannon's idea of information seriously, we suggest that there should be an information decoder function $F(p(e_i))$ whose average using $p(e_i)$ should reproduce the two average moments used to statistically describe the system, i.e.

$$F(p(e_i)) = a e_i + b \quad ((5)) \quad \text{of} \quad \sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = \sum_i a e_i p(e_i) + b \sum_i p(e_i)$$

The basic idea is then to have a stable average of information. If

$$p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i) \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{Then } \sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i) + dp(e_i)) = \sum_i a e_i \{p(e_i) + dp(e_i)\} + b \{p(e_i) + dp(e_i)\} \quad ((7))$$

The use of the decoder function $F(p(e_i))$ allows one to pick out a unique stable solution because one knows mathematically how F changes with $p+dp$ using a Taylor series. This leads to the two conditions:

$$dp(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = (a e_i + b) dp(e_i) \quad ((8a))$$

$$dp(e_i) p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) = \text{constant} * dp(e_i) \quad ((8b))$$

Summing ((8b)) yields 0 so one has a stable solution essentially given by ((8b)) because $F = \ln(p)$ is a solution.

In other words, statistically $p(e_i)$ (the equilibrium solution) describes all information in the system and one then needs to extract it using a decoder function.

$\ln(p)$ is not the only solution in this case. One may see that

$$F = p(e_i)^q \quad ((9))$$

is also a solution if one suggests that an alternative to ((8b)) is

$$dp(e_i) p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) = \text{constant} * F(p(e_i)) \quad ((8c))$$

. This, however, leads to an interesting situation because q is an extra piece of information not contained in the constraint (or moment of e_i) statistical description. In principle, the information described by the moments $\sum_i p(e_i)$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ should be identical to the information contained in $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$. The decoder should not have extra q information. One may, however, remedy this by suggesting a situation in which q is present in the moments, i.e. by using

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \sum_i p(e_i)^q e_i = E_{ave} \quad ((10))$$

Then one may use: $\sum_i p(e_i)^q F(p(e_i))$ as the decoder average with $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$.

As a result, the Tsallis case is part of the decoder solution along with the Maxwell-Boltzmann one. The decoder approach places all of the information in $p(e_i)$ and then mathematically tries to pull it out in order to statistically describe the system. We suggest that this viewpoint is more general than using Shannon's entropy or maximization of the number of states subject to constraints.

Mathematical Link Between $d/dx \ln(x)$ and $d/dx x$ power n

We have suggested above that two solutions arise from the information decoder approach. We suggest that this follows because the decoder function derivative is used in $p \, dF/dp = \text{constant}$ or $p \, dF/dp = \text{constant} \cdot F$. This result suggests a solution of $\ln(p)$ for the first case and p power q for the second. We note that $d/dx \ln(x)$ is associated with $d/dx x$ power n in that the latter can only produce the series of powers:

... 3, 2, 1, 0, -2, -3, -4 ... while $d/dx \ln(x)$ produces -1 ((11))

Thus, $d/dx \ln(x)$ is linked to $d/dx x$ power n through this series of derivatives and it is not surprising that both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and the Tsallis results arise.

Conclusion

In conclusion, instead of using maximization of the \ln of the number of states subject to constraints (and Stirling's approximation) or maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to the same constraints or reaction balance, we propose an information decoder approach. The information decoder method is based on the idea that there is a specific unique $p(e_i)$ equilibrium distribution which describes all of the statistical information in the system when acted upon by a decoder function. We suggest that the problem of an ideal gas is solved in terms of statistical information as it is a statistical problem. In particular, what one calls the constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = \text{eave}$ are statistical average moments of e_i power 0 and e_i power 1. A decoder function average should describe this same information, i.e. $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ means $F(p(e_i)) = a e_i + b$, but the information decoder should be stable to $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$. This leads to $p(e_i) \, dF/dp(e_i) = \text{constant}$. $\ln(p)$, the Maxwell-Boltzmann result is an immediate solution, but one might also consider the result $p(e_i) \, dF/dp(e_i) = \text{constant} \cdot F(p(e_i))$ from an information point of view. This yields $F = p(e_i)$ power q . The same information that exists in the average moments (constraints) should exist in $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$. We thus suggest using $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$, $\sum_i p(e_i)$ power $q \, F(p(e_i))$ with $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and $\sum_i p(e_i)$ power $q \, e_i = \text{eave}$. This then leads to $p \, dF/dp = 1$ with $F = (1-p)$ power $(1-q) / (1-q)$. For $q=1$, i.e. removing the information about q , one should obtain the MB result, so $F = \ln(p)$ when $q > 1$.